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“THE LIFE OF A BREADWINNER”

I wake at dawn and work till late,
To fill the pots and stock the plate.
Each coin I earn, I hold with care,
Yet still, it vanishes into air.
I see a shirt, I long to buy,
But walk away with a heavy sigh.
For how can I indulge in me,
When there are needs I fail to see?
They ask for things, their hearts delight,
I try my best with all my might.
And when I can't, the words they say,
Cut deep inside and dull my day.
I borrow just to make ends meet,
Yet still, they want more treats.
A cycle spinning, never done,
A race I run but never won.
I set aside my dreams, my needs,
To grant them joy, to plant good seeds.
But do they see the nights I weep,
The weight I bear, the pain so deep?
Oh, family dear, please understand,
These pockets hold no magic hand.
Be kind with words, don't let them sting,
For I have given everything.
If I lived just for myself,
My pay would rest upon my shelf.
But love has made me give, not save,
A willing heart, yet still a slave.
And one day, when I give no more,
Will I be cast outside the door?
For now, I stand, though weak inside,
A breadwinner with wounded pride.